

Personalised Prognostics and Diagnostics for Improved Decision Support in Cardiovascular Diseases

Data Management Plan (D5.1)

Document Information

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1. Description of the data

1.1. Background

This document covers the Data Management Plan of the ERA PerMed project PerCard (Personalised Prognostics and Diagnostics for Improved Decision Support in Cardiovascular Diseases) that has started on 1 January 2022 and is planned to run for three years. The project is a co-operation between four European partners (Tampere University, Finland; Polytechnic University of Milan, Italy; Centro Cardiologico Monzino, Italy; and Protestant University of Applied Sciences, Ludwigsburg, Germany). PerCard explores the value of combining integrated heterogeneous data sources with AI/ML to increase the validity of risk assessment for cardiovascular disease in different populations. The consortium develops specialised models for populations as well as explicitly mitigates the issue of gender-bias in existing risk assessment methods. Emphasis is put on methods that are easily transferable from research to practice and accessible and affordable for the wide population. PerCard develops and uses new data analysis methods (AI, ML, signal processing, including ensemble classifiers and Bayesian neural networks) to develop more powerful risk assessment methods that are accurate, robust, and explainable. The project provides advancements especially in the field of explainable AI and AI for time-series analysis. PerCard delivers an integrated decision support system for understandable personalised risk/prognosis assessment of morbidity and mortality in cardiovascular settings and tests this robustly in retrospective and prospective settings. End-users are involved throughout the entire research, development and validation process. ELSA considerations, including gender, accessibility to all, ethics of AI and decision support are an inherent part of the project. To capitalise on earlier investments and speed up development, PerCard re-uses large retrospective databases to start with (Finland, Italy). PerCard uses robust validation methods to guarantee generalisability, combining independent test sets as well as prospective test data collection as truly independent reference.

This version of the document provides the Data Management Plan with information as available at the start of the project (March 2022). In this three-year research project, it is expected that new findings and opportunities will influence data properties and processes. Hence this document may be updated as the project and its information evolve.

1.2. Type of study

PerCard will carry out two studies within its project duration by using existing databases and new data acquired as follows:

- *Retrospective study:* By exploiting 4 databases, namely Fincavas (4600 subjs), Young Finns (3500 subjs), Health 2000 (8100 subjs) and retrospective data from Centro Cardiologico Monzino (CCM) (1100 subjs), PerCard pursues the re-use of earlier efforts to generate new value from truly heterogeneous data sources, and so to achieve a fast-track development to guarantee results in the early project phases. The specific objective of the retrospective study is to increase the valid applicability of risk assessment for cardiovascular diseases in different genetic populations. Prior to database exploitation, the data available will be harmonized, that includes common definition

of endpoints and pursuing common data standards (e.g. OMOP-OHDSI), to generate the PerCard data catalogue from the four databases' information.

- Prospective study: The validation and refinement of the AI models generated in the retrospective study will be conducted by using the prospective data gathered in CCM. Specifically, this validation in a prospective setting will assess an integrated decision support system (DSS) for understandable personalised risk and prognosis assessment of morbidity and mortality in cardiovascular settings. In addition, the use of independent databases will provide the opportunity to perform a rigorous validation of the DSS and a wide applicability of the outcomes defined. We plan to collect roughly 900 patients with suspect of cardiovascular disease or having CVD risk factors (diabetes, hypertension, genetic background, smoking, diet habits and life-style) which will undergo screening analysis at CCM for the duration of the collecting period. The follow-up part of the study (3 years) will be continued also after the end of the project for the last enrolled patients to optimize clinical usefulness and scientific value of the investment.

Further information about the prospective study can be found in the following Table 1:

Table 1: Information about exploratory clinical (prospective) studies conducted in PerCard

APPLICANT/COORDINATING INVESTIGATOR	Claudio Tondo, MD, PhD Centro Cardiologico Monzino, IRCCS, University of Milan Tel: +39-02-58002480; Fax: +39-02-58002782 e-mail: claudio.tondo@ccfm.it ; claudio.tondo@unimi.it
TITLE OF STUDY	<i>Identification of risk factors for cardiovascular diseases in general population in relation to gender, genetic background, life styling, diet habits, demographics, etc</i>
CONDITION	<i>Cardiovascular diseases</i>
OBJECTIVE(S)	<i>Which principal research questions are to be addressed? The amount of clinical data retrospectively and prospectively analyzed would constitute the basis for promoting a robust risk assessment method. This would define the clinical actions to be implemented and considering AI as a novel tool in healthcare management</i>
INTERVENTION(S)	<i>Brief description of the experimental and the control treatments or interventions, if applicable: dose and mode of application.</i> <u>Experimental intervention:</u> use retrospective (from a large database) and prospective clinical data <u>Control intervention:</u> Not needed <u>Duration of intervention per patient:</u> 3 years <u>Follow-up per patient:</u> 3 years (including retrospective patients)

KEY INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA	<p><u>Key inclusion criteria:</u> Suspect cardiovascular diseases or Risk Factors</p> <p><u>Key exclusion criteria:</u> < 18 yrs>80 yrs; any previous cardiac interventions/therapy</p>
OUTCOME(S)	<p><u>Primary efficacy endpoint:</u> identification of valid risk assessment method for cardiovascular diseases</p> <p><u>Key secondary endpoint(s):</u> identification of clinical/social actions to reduce risk for cardiovascular diseases</p> <p><u>Assessment of safety:</u> strict follow-up</p>
STUDY TYPE	<i>Retrospective and prospective observational study</i>
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS	<p><u>Efficacy:</u></p> <p><u>Description of the primary efficacy analysis and population:</u> The performance of the novel risk assessment algorithms will be compared with the performance of established algorithms (i.e. Framingham Risk Score) by ROC-curve AUC, Harrell concordance statistics, Net Reclassification Improvement (NRI) and by Integrated discrimination improvement (IDI).</p> <p><u>Safety:</u> <i>n.a.</i></p> <p><u>Secondary endpoints:</u></p>
SAMPLE SIZE	<p><u>To be assessed for eligibility (n =2000)</u></p> <p><u>To be allocated to trial (n =1200)</u></p> <p><u>To be analysed (n = 900)</u></p> <p>Assuming a total of 2000 patients followed for an average of 7 years and 1.5% yearly event incidence in the retrospective CCM database, we expect about 210 events. By simulation analysis, with that number of events we estimated a power of 95% to deem as significant the comparison of an algorithm with a ROC AUC of about 0.63 (e.g the Framingham Risk Score) and a new classifier with a ROC AUC of about 0.70.</p>
TRIAL DURATION	<p><u>Time for preparation of the trial (months): 2 months</u></p> <p><u>Recruitment period (months): 10 months</u></p> <p><u>First patient in to last patient out (months): 46 months</u></p> <p><u>Time for data clearance and analysis (months): 3 months</u></p> <p><u>Duration of the entire trial (months): 51 months</u></p>

PARTICIPATING CENTERS	<u>To be involved (n): if applicable; how many centres will be involved?</u> <i>Please also list the cities.</i> <i>Centro Cardiologico Monzino (CCM), University of Milan, Milan, Italy</i>
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In addition, Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspects (ELSA) of the project will be analysed in a dedicated work package. To that purpose, different social science research activities will be conducted (and generate data) through interviews and focus group discussions with researchers, clinicians, patients, and other stakeholders to generate AI recommendations on AI in CVD risk assessment.

1.3. Types of data

PerCard leverages the use of large retrospective databases to bring a unique opportunity to innovate and allow fast-track development and thorough validation in a transnational setting of CVD risk prediction model. The data is summarised in Table 2. The Fincavas database comprises rich data, including over 4500 15-lead exercise ECG recordings, hemodynamics as well as lifestyle information and genomic data, 39% of the recordings are from female subjects. Endpoint data (morbidity, mortality) is collected periodically. The Young Finns longitudinal database on its part offers data to advance the prognostics and risk assessment based on features available already during young age. The Health 2000 database comprises over 8000 individuals who participated in a health examination, especially designed to reflect the population characteristics with a stratified approach. The retrospective data collected at CCM comprises more than 1100 patients followed for many years and enables effective cross-population clinical analysis and validation of relevant biomarkers between populations.

Table 2 also provides a full overview of the data being collected and processed. Data that is being generated includes features extracted from the different time-series data, capturing time-frequency and time-frequency descriptors; indices (e.g class probabilities, outcome estimators) based on combining different data and processing them with data-analytics measures (machine learning, AI, and signal processing). Additionally, data is being collected in the form of user and patient interviews / audio transcripts.

Table 2: Overview of the retrospective and prospective data to be used in PerCard

	Fincavas Pirkanmaa Hospital District	Young Finns University of Turku	Health 2000 Finnish Inst Health & Welf	CCM retrospective CCM	CCM prospective CCM
short description	Risk profiles using genetic, haemodynamic and ECG markers	Prognostics in younger population	Population characteristics with stratification		
total N	4600	3500	8100	1100	900
females	39 %	50 %	55 %	50 %	50 %
Follow up duration	13-20 years	30 years	20 years	average 7 years	3+ years
Frequency of assessments	2	8	2	every 6 months	every 6 months
age (average, range) years	56 (11:85)	3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 age coh >30		18-80	18-80
patient history	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
prior diseases	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
medication	yes	partly	yes	yes	yes
risk factors for CHD	partly	yes	yes	yes	yes
family history	no			yes	yes
exercise ECG	4566	no	no		
HR	yes, continuous	yes	yes	yes,	yes
BP	yes, every 2 minutes	yes	yes	yes, every 2 minutes	yes, every 2 minutes
MET	yes, maximal	no	no		
coronary angiography/CT scan	1615	obtainable	obtainable	obtainable	obtainable
resting ECG	4566	7349	8100	all	all
other physiological data	yes (weight, height, waist)	yes	yes	yes	yes
lifestyle data	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
laboratory data	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
genomic information	4566	7349	8100	yes	yes
Outcome measures					
morbidity	obtainable	obtainable	obtainable	yes	yes
mortality	458 (2011), 1300 (2021)	obtainable	obtainable	yes	yes
mortality - SCD	80 (2011)	obtainable	obtainable	yes	yes
infarcts	obtainable	obtainable	obtainable	yes	yes
operations (bypasses etc)	obtainable	obtainable	obtainable	yes	yes
	Niemenen et al 2006	youngfinnsstudy.utu.fi	Rankinen et al 2020	Banerjee et al 2016	PerCard proposal

WP4 will carry out a set of interviews and focus groups with different healthcare stakeholders to gather information and experiences about the ELSA aspects of the project. This research is two-fold entailing a qualitative and quantitative analysis.

1.4. Format and scale of the data

- The content of Finnish databases (Fincavas, YoungFinns and Health2000) can be provided in a tabular data form, e.g. in csv format which helps to process it in general programming languages. Particularly, all data related to medical assessment (ECG, Angiography scans, etc.) are provided in the appropriate data formats given by the device used for measuring. An exhaustive description of the variables and format considered in Fincavas can be found in the file "*Fincavas variables.pdf*" accessible in PerCard project space through this [link](#). As regards YoungFinns, the file "*Young Finns - ALL VARIABLES 1980-2018*" ([link](#)) offers a detailed summary of the information stored in the database.
- CCM database is provided by means of a Microsoft Access database file that allows to make queries to obtain specific information in a exported file format of csv or xlsx. The list of variables as well as its information associated is stored in the file '*List of variabili in DBase CCM with comments for EraPerMed.xlsx*' ([link](#))

- The ELSA research will collect information by means of audio files of interviews and focus group discussions, which will be transcribed into text format and then be stored for its further analysis during the project execution

Interoperability data issues are covered by following the FAIR principles (See section 2.4). The PerCard project intends to produce interoperable data that allows data exchange and reuse between researchers, institutions, organisations, etc., as well as being compliant with available (open) software applications.

2. Data collection/generation/reuse

2.1. Will the project reuse data?

Yes No

PerCard envisages the use of existing databases in the retrospective study carried out within the project. Three different Finnish retrospective databases, and one Italian retrospective database will be used in the early phase of the project handled as agreed with the data controllers and owners, following GDPR regulations and national requirements (e.g., Finnish act on secondary use of health and social data). Negotiations and permissions processes have started to access and make proper use of such data. In addition, data will be available as agreed within protected computing environments within the consortium.

As regards ELSA research, the reuse of data is not considered.

2.2. New data / data management

The new data collected is aimed at being analysed in the prospective study described in Sec 1.1. Prospective data will be collected, processed and stored following GDPR requirements and with the approval of the local ethics committee of the IRCCS Istituto Europeo di Oncologia (IEO) and Centro Cardiologico Monzino (CCM), accredited by the Lombardy Region and the National Medicinal Agency.

In case of need, separate agreements will be made regarding access of the original data for further use, since the intent is to make as much of the data accessible as possible, while adhering to the restrictions for the retrospective data as well as prospective data (follow-up continues also after PerCard formal end). Generated data, such as novel features, models, risk scores, visualisations etc resulting from the data will be made available adhering to anonymisation requirements.

WP4 (Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspects) aims to achieve acceptability for AI-based applications in/for cardiovascular medicine in society. WP4 interacts with all other work packages throughout the project. Specifically, WP4 will require new data from interviews and focus group discussions in order to deduce strategies to achieve acceptability for AI-based applications in and for cardiovascular medicine in society. An application for the ELSA study will be handed in to the responsible ethics review boards. All interviewees will be asked for their informed consent regarding interviewing, transcription, and analysis.

2.3. Methodologies for data collection / generation

In the retrospective study, the objective of “T1.2: Retrospective data combination and catalogue preparation” will be to generate the PerCard data catalogue with all data harmonized and annotated with the relevant outcomes defined in Task 1.1 (Study definition, ethical guidance) aimed to translate clinical questions to data-analytics requirements. The catalogue will collect information from the following databases: Fincavas (4600 subs), Young Finns (3500 subs), Health 2000 (8100 subs), CCM retrospective (1500 subs).

During “T1.3: Prospective data collection”, we plan to collect roughly 900 patients with suspect of cardiovascular disease and having CVD risk factors (diabetes, hypertension, genetic background, smoking, diet habits and life-style) which will undergo screening analysis at CCM for the duration of the collecting period. Data that is being generated includes features extracted from the different time-series data, capturing time-frequency and time-frequency descriptors; indices (e.g class probabilities, outcome estimators) based on combining different data and processing them with data-analytics measures (machine learning, AI, and signal processing). Additionally, data is being collected in the form of user and patient interviews / transcripts and recordings of workshops.

The follow-up part of the study (3 years) will be continued also after the end of the project for the last enrolled patients to optimize clinical usefulness and scientific value of the investment.

In an ELSA integration workshop all partners as well as external experts reflect and comment on social and ethical issues in a structured and moderated discourse about AI in cardiovascular medicine. Interviews are conducted with researchers, clinicians, patients, and other stakeholders regarding topics identified in T4.1 (ELSA integration). Interview results are deduced by qualitative content analysis. Patient are involved to introduce patient perspectives into the interview guidelines and pretests. The aim is to include at least twenty subjects in individual interviews and at least ten subjects in focus group discussions. Selected topics from T4.1, T4.2 (Qualitative social science research) and T4.3 (ELSA consultation) are investigated by quantitative methods. Standardized instruments are identified, and appropriate questionnaires are developed to examine clinicians and (former or potential) patients. The aim is to include at least one hundred subjects.

The PerCard workplan is detailed in the Annex I

2.4. Data quality and standards

Concerning the work with the existing databases, the harmonization procedure includes common definition of endpoints and common data formats (OMOP-OHDSI). The OMOP Common Data Model allows for the systematic analysis of disparate observational databases. The concept behind this approach is to transform data contained within those databases into a common format (data model) as well as a common representation (terminologies, vocabularies, coding schemes), and then perform systematic analyses using a library of standard analytic routines that have been written based on the common format.

For the new data captured in the project (prospective study, ELSA research study), different best practices will be adopted in terms of data quality:

- Ensuring that no data are accidentally changed and that the accuracy of data is maintained over the entire project life cycle.
- Adopting and enforcing formal version control processes with, for instance, simply shared and documented file naming conventions.
- Transcriptions of audio or video interviews should be checked by someone other than the transcriber.
- Analog material should be digitised in the highest resolution possible for accuracy.
- In all conversions, maintaining the original information content should be ensured.

The most relevant standards regarding data handling, in this experimental context with patients, concern the area of ethics, data protection and privacy; and are listed below:

- Directive 95/46/EC: Protection of individuals regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.
- Art. 7, 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights
- Art. 8 European Convention on Human Rights
- Case Law by the European Court of Human Rights
- GDPR regulation (2016/679).
- WMA Declaration of Helsinki
- For the data itself we use accepted standards as HL7 ([Health Level Seven International - Homepage | HL7 International](#)) and OMOP-OHDSI (<https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/the-common-data-model/>).
- For designing and reporting the multi-variate prediction models we adhere to the TRIPOD guidelines (<https://www.tripod-statement.org/>).
- The quantitative and qualitative data from the empirical social science research in work package WP4 is managed according to the research and GDPR regulations in Germany and the EU.

3. Data management, documentation and curation

3.1. Managing, storing and curating data.

The Guidelines for Data Management in Horizon 2020 and ECRIN certification standards that entail IT Standards and Data Management Standards will be used as guidance. The European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) has published these requirements for data centres to provide high quality, compliant and safe data management, as well as effective management of the underlying systems and IT infrastructure.

PerCard will analyse three existing Finnish databases for the retrospective study whose data curation has already been carried out at their respective sites whose organisations act as data controllers. In addition, CCM acts as data controller for their retrospective database, and they will also be responsible of

controlling and preserving the new data collected in the prospective study. Combining of data, quality and consistency checks is done in Tasks 1.2 and 1.3 by PerCard partners who have long-standing experience in the needed methods.

Concerning ELSA research studies, the information gathered in the interviews and workshops will be controlled and preserved by following FAIR principles (see section 2.4).

PerCard is dedicated to making the results available to the community. Software is open sourced. The prospectively collected databases will be made available as FAIR as possible, considering both GDPR and interest of the research community. PUL is leading the task by overseeing that FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles are addressed to. TUNI, POLIMI and CCM provide the results (and documentations) to be shared following these principles. Thus, the following table expresses the actions considered in PerCard project to commit FAIR principles

Table 3. Implementation of FAIR principles in PerCard

Findable
<p>Data needs to be findable for other to be reused. Thus, the following action will pursue in PerCard: (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier that allows for precise referencing of variables and datasets; data are described with rich metadata; metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes; (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.</p> <p>In particular, the The PerCard catalogue (T2.1) will follow this convention to allow a unique reference for the variables defined. Moreover, Data and metadata depositions will be assigned persistent and unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI; www.doi.org). DOI is a technical and social infrastructure coordinated by the International DOI Foundation (IDF) based on the ISO 26324 standard to ease the findability of specified digital assets.</p> <p>Metadata from PerCard will be indexed in Zenodo's search engine after publishing. To generate the metadata the standard ISO 15836 will be followed which specify 15 core elements to describes the data: contributor; coverage; creator; date; description; format; identifier; language; publisher; relation; rights; source; subject; title; type</p>
Accessible
<p>After project data is obtained, potential new users need to know how the data can be accessible. The access principles are: (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol; the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable; the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary; metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.</p> <p>After the embargo period (see below), the PerCard project data will be available through the Zenodo platform or through direct connection with PerCard consortium members. PerCard will prioritize data in open formats that can be accessed on open-source software wherever possible to ease the access. Documentation in PerCard will be provided in the Portable Document Format (PDF) or as text files (.txt).</p>
Interoperable
In the PerCard project simple data interoperability is also essential to utilize effective workflows

for analysis, storage and processing of the data. Thus, points to be considered are: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation; (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles ; (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Reusable

To be reusable, data and metadata needs to be findable, accessible and interoperable. In addition, data reuse licenses and other restrictions needs to be clarified. The FAIR principles concerning reusability establishes: Meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attribute; Meta(data) are released with a clear and accessible data usage license; Meta(data) are associated with detailed provenance; Meta(data) meet domain-relevant community standards.

Data embargo: The PerCard consortium will agree during project execution on the embargo period for the PerCard data usage reserved for the PerCard consortium partners. The data will not be made available for research outside the PerCard consortium during this period. This embargo is in place to ensure the PerCard partners get sufficient time to complete ongoing research and publications.

Reuse of identifiable data: Identifiable information (data that contains elements of personally identifying information sufficient to allow identification of individuals) requires special protection in accordance with GDPR Article 9(1), and research participants needs to approve processing in study consent forms.

Reuse of anonymized data: with anonymization the possibility of identifying individuals in a dataset is removed, so it is possible to extract knowledge without the risk of individuals identification. To that aim, the PerCard consortium will rely on recognized guidelines for those project works where anonymization is needed. All patient data is reported as anonymized in the project deliverables and in peer reviewed publications. Anonymous individual quotes captured in WP4 can also be used in these reports.

Metadata standards and data documentation

Data produced and/or used in the project will be discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers). In addition, search keywords will be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use.

PerCard project data will be documented with a content- or discipline-specific metadata record. The data generated by the project will arise from a number of different interrelated fields, therefore not a single metadata standard will apply to all the cases, but we will work with data generators to identify suitable standards from the Research Data Alliance Metadata Standards Directory ([Metadata Standards Directory WG | RDA \(rd-alliance.org\)](#)). In addition, Qvain tool can be used to describe project data and generate metadata ([Qvain – Research Dataset Description Tool | Fairdata](#)). Metadata from PerCard will be indexed in Zenodo's search engine after publishing. As a baseline approach, to generate the metadata the standard ISO 15836 will be followed which specify 15 core elements to describes the data: contributor; coverage; creator; date; description; format; identifier; language; publisher; relation; rights; source; subject; title; type

3.2. Data preservation strategy and standards

Preserving the data sometimes is equally treated as the process of storing data, however in PerCard data preservation best practices will be adopted as a process to guarantee a durable management for the stored data. In a wider definition, preservation of data defines the process of formulating and defining the ways to guarantee that the data will remain intact during the time and that it will remain useful for the same purpose for which it was created and stored. Some general characteristics about the data in this process can be summarized as follows: migrate the data to best format, migrate the data to a suitable medium, back-up stored data to preserve the information, create metadata and documentation for the stored data, archive data in a defined physical or virtual medium.

Data generated within the project will be preserved as local storage in secure environments at the local owners' sites. This data will be stored in those sites for a duration of 20 years. During this period, maintenance labours to ensure data integrity and security will be followed.

Project generated data, documents, etc that do not entail any sensitive or personal information will be shared by following FAIR and open science principles in the certified Zenodo data archive (<https://zenodo.org/>). In addition, to be aligned with the open-source initiative and leverage the related research community, the software packages and AI models developed in PerCard will also be made available via GitHub. These certified repositories were selected since they assure long term preservation as well as security and robustness capabilities.

3.3. Allocation of resources

The need for data management continues after the project (and funding period) ends. The PerCard partners will continue to use the data generated in the project to produce scientific papers, and to make project data available for others. These efforts are dependent on allocation of resources. The project's partners have estimated the allocation of resources aimed mainly to the open-access publications under the concept of 'Other direct costs' (total budgeted costs 89.098€). The specific figure dedicated to open-access publications can be calculated at the end of the project. Moreover, the use of open data repositories (Zenodo, Github) is intended to be free. Nevertheless, the task T3.4 aims at discussing the sustainability of the project's results according to FAIR principles and exploring the post-project expansion of the scope. Thus, any modification of the resources allocation could be arisen from the works and results of this task.

4. Data security and confidentiality of potentially disclosive information

4.1. Formal information/data security standards

There are 3 sorts of data being handled within PerCard:

1. Retrospective patient data on cardiac risk as performed in Finland (FINCAVAS, Young Finns and Health 200 studies) and in Italy (data collected at CCM). See Table 1 for details. The retrospective

data is managed by data controllers at Pirkanmaa hospital district, Turku University Hospital, Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, and CCM respectively. All data is stored and managed adhering to GDPR guidelines, and collected in adherence to the WMA Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association. (2013). World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *Jama*, 310(20), 2191-2194.) and national legislations as well as following approval of local ethics committees. Access to the Finnish data will be in adherence with the Finnish Act on Secondary Use of Health and Social Data 552/2019.

2. Prospective data to be collected by CCM (details in "Exploratory Clinical Studies" form). A study plan will be submitted for approval to the Ethics committee of the IRCCS Istituto Europeo di Oncologia (IEO) and Centro Cardiologico Monzino (CCM), accredited by the Lombardy Region and the National Medicinal Agency. Full informed consent will be obtained allowing sharing of data after anonymization. All data collected will adhere to GDPR regulations regarding data access, privacy and subjects' rights to withdraw from the study at any moment. The study size has been calculated using a power analysis based on simulation with findings from the retrospective study.
3. Data collected in WP4 from interviews and focus group discussions to establish the ELSA framework. Data from interviewees in the format of audio recordings and transcripts are only collected with full prior consent of all participants. The data are handled and analyzed with pseudonyms and handling adheres fully to GDPR regulations. The data are reported without pseudonyms, i.e. anonymously to the public, in publications.

Study participants that donate (or "lend") their data to research needs to be informed about potential benefits and harms through consent forms. A fundamental right is for the participant's to at any time withdraw their consent and have their data removed from future analyses and scientific publications. The right to withdraw consent is in practice limited from the point where researchers are allowed or required to anonymize the data; it is impossible to identify individuals in anonymized data and thus to remove individual study participant that withdraw their consent.

Data privacy deals with the study participant's right to control their own data, right to confidentiality, and minimization of risk. A number of steps are taken in research to protect the data donor's privacy and minimize risks of data breaches. For example, by using de-identified data where the researchers do not have access to the coupling key, publishing results at group level and only collecting or using data necessary for the purpose of the research (data minimization).

The core elements of data security are confidentiality, integrity and availability (ISO 27001): (i) Confidentiality aims to ensure that data is accessible only by authorized individuals; (ii) Integrity aims to ensure that data is both reliable and accurate; and (iii) Availability aims to ensure that data is accessible in accordance with identified needs.

In PerCard project, names, address, dates directly related to an individual, phone and fax numbers, e-mail addresses, numbers of social security, care record, insurance beneficiary, account, certificate and license, biometric identifiers, full face photographic images and any comparable images etc., are considered as complete or partial identifier data. To protect the identity of participants;

- All the materials gathered through user studies will be treated as non-identifiable,
- If written personal data will exist, after its transfer to an electronic database, all of it will be destroyed (this measure excludes the consent forms),
- The personal information about the participants will be kept in confidence and will be made anonymous, by the data entity that collected the data, following the local IT and security practices at the respective site.
- Personal identifiers will be replaced with a numerical code (pseudonymization),
- The data is only distributed with the pseudonyms to the project participants for analysis, so that the project participants cannot deduce the identities.
- In all electronic systems, there will be no possibility to associate identification code with the name of a participant. Nevertheless, in ELSA research this code will be kept physically during the analysis phases

4.2. Main risks to data security

Data management is directly connected with issues of privacy and as such it should be aiming to the efficient and early identification of risks and their timely solution through appropriate strategies. Initially, the data objects need to be categorized based on the identifying and sensitive information that they contain in order to select the appropriate mitigation strategies. After categorizing the data objects, the risks related to each category should be determined.

Some of the risks estimated at the initial project phase in terms of data security are:

- Catastrophic loss of all data on site prior to periodical backups; Mitigation – Extremely low probability event. Most data will also reside at local partner sites and a time backup period is in place to minimize exposure of data loss.
- Data access by unauthorised 3rd party; Mitigation – Access to data repository would be by partners only and require secure passwords or other security mechanism (eg. two-factor authentication). Cloud data storage will be strongly encrypted with access restricted to the consortium partners or the dataset owners only (depending on the agreements made).
- Delays due to obtaining formal data sharing agreements, administrative processes, different local interpretations of GDPR. Likelihood moderate, severity moderate. Mitigation: preparing for agreements and sharing has already started in proposal writing phase to allow ample time. Several of the databases can be accessed locally in any case and early derived results can be generated and shared for novel algorithm and model development.

5. Data sharing and access

Since the project data will be stored in databases at different locations, the software needed to access data will be derived from the specific database tools employed (i.e. Microsoft access, Mongo DB, etc.). Regarding software to process the information and build the machine learning models generic applications or language programming as, respectively, MATLAB, Python or R are needed. Additional package or libraries (Keras, Tensorflow, SciKit learn, SHAP, PDPbox) that facilitate the signal processing, data reading or explainable models' development are also considered.

Qualitative information will be recorded in text-based document formats, including MS Word, Open Document Format and PDF. Quantitative data will be stored in MS Excel and CSV format. In addition, other kind of information related to bio signals or medical information will use the proper data format generated by the dedicated software.

5.1. Suitability for sharing

Members of the consortium are fully committed to sharing results (software, documents, and generated data) and bundle forces to advance international research and development. PerCard members are e.g. active in the OMOP-HDSI initiative aiming to standardise data (<https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/the-common-data-model/>) and in the European-wide Joint Action TEHDAS Towards the European Health Data Space (<https://www.sitra.fi/en/projects/joint-action-towards-the-european-health-data-space-tehdas/>).

The information and data suitable for sharing will be delivered under Creative Commons version 4.0 license or equivalent by using the certified data repositories Zenodo (non-sensitive/personal data, project deliverables) and GitHub. All data shared will comply with GDPR directive in terms of data security, privacy and governance. By adopting the Creative Commons version 4.0 license or equivalent, any third party that might want to use PerCard shared data should take the following actions ([Creative Commons — Attribution 4.0 International — CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)):

- Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
- No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

External researcher under this license are free to:

- Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format
- Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

On the other hand, data related to datasets (original patient data) is not expected to be shared to external researchers during and after the project. This decision might be discussed during the project execution. Nevertheless, given the risk of disclosure of personal data (which is particularly sensitive due to the medical nature of the research topic), raw data from the user engagements will not be made publicly available.

Any patient data gathered during the prospective study will be treated as sensitive personal data, and access and sharing by the project's researchers will be strictly limited according to the EU Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC). As a general principle, only pseudonymised data will be shared after specific consent or approval given, on the basis that the recipient cannot disclose the data and is not permitted to link the data with other data which might render the information more identifiable.

Other generated data, such as novel features, models, risk scores, visualisations etc resulting from the data will be made available adhering to anonymisation requirements.

5.2. Discovery by potential users of the research data

All non-restricted materials generated under the PerCard project will be disseminated in accordance with the policies of the participating institutions. These materials may also be transferred to other institutions or individuals under specific terms depending on the policies of the relevant organisations. In general, the material will be published either during or at the end of the project, consistent with normal scientific and institutional practices. Non-sensitive research data which documents, supports or validates research findings will be published after the main research findings have been accepted for publication. Apart from the local storage in audited secure environments at the local owners' sites, project generated data, documents etc will be maintained at <https://zenodo.org/> and the PerCard project website ([PerCard project: Personalised Prognostics and Diagnostics for Improved Decision Support in Cardiovascular Diseases | Tampere universities \(tuni.fi\)](#)). Software packages will also be made available via GitHub.

PerCard is dedicated to making the results available to the community. Software is open sourced. The prospectively collected databases will be made available as FAIR as possible, considering both GDPR and interest of the research community. PUL is leading the task T3.4 and the WP4 by overseeing that FAIR principles are addressed to. TUNI, POLIMI and CCM provide the results (and documentations) to be shared following these principles.

To this end, the Findable measures proposed in FAIR principles can be applied i.e.:

- In particular, the The PerCard catalogue (T2.1) will follow this convention to allow a unique reference for the variables defined in it. Moreover, Data and metadata depositions will be assigned persistent and unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI; www.doi.org). DOI is a technical and social infrastructure coordinated by the International DOI Foundation (IDF) based on the ISO 26324 standard to ease the findability of specified digital assets.
- Metadata from PerCard will be indexed in Zenodo's search engine after publishing. To generate the metadata the standard ISO 15836 will be followed which specify 15 core elements to describes the data: contributor; coverage; creator; date; description; format; identifier; language; publisher; relation; rights; source; subject; title; type.

The documents and results of the project will be made available through the mentioned dissemination channels in order to support their discoverability. Furthermore, all scientific publications of the project will provide links to the respective results and documents on the PerCard repository in Zenodo and GitHub platform.

5.3. Governance of access

PerCard will employ the open repositories like Zenodo and GitHub for sharing the results and project generated data (except concerning sensitive and personal/patient data). Thus, since these repositories are open access, there will not be any special governance mechanism for external researchers to access information stored in those repositories. Nevertheless, the license under the project contents are shared

is Creative Commons 4.0 ([Creative Commons — Attribution 4.0 International — CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)), thus, external researcher must commit rules of this license when using PerCard results.

The consortium agreement signed by all the parties specifies the terms and conditions pertaining to ownership, access rights, exploitation of background and results and dissemination of results. The decision on making data available to potential new users will be made by the management board of PerCard.

5.4. The study team's exclusive use of the data

In general, The information/data intended to be shared will be published either during or at the end of the project in the repository mentioned above. By doing so, PerCard pursues to adopt a proactive attitude according to FAIR and open science principles, and so to start to impact on research and scientific communities at early stages of the project.

The PerCard consortium will agree during project execution on the duration of the embargo period for the PerCard data usage reserved for the PerCard consortium partners. The data will not be made available for research outside the PerCard consortium in this period. This embargo is in place to ensure the PerCard partners get sufficient time to complete ongoing research and publications.

5.5. Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

Data sharing restriction will be carried out according to the partners agreement (see 5.1 section).

For ELSA research, consent for audio file sharing will not be obtained neither for transcript sharing (even after removal of personal information). Quotations modified from transcript will only be reported in publications.

The restrictions in data sharing to external project parties will be established by the Creative Commons 4.0 license adopted. The delay to sharing the agreed project data to external parties will accomplish the embargo period define by the PerCard's partners.

- Regulation of responsibilities of users

Clinical or patient data will not be intended to be shared with external users. Concerning other project data and documentation, external users that access and employ such information must strictly follow the terms expressed in the Creative Commons version 4.0 license or equivalent adopted by PerCard.

6. Responsibilities

Every partner is responsible for the data they are collecting and generating in terms of study-wide data management, metadata creation, data security, quality assurance of data. This is valid for both personal and non-personal data. The data has been collected, combined, stored and transmitted according to the relevant national, European and institutional regulations.

7. Relevant institutional, departmental or study policies on data sharing and data security

Policy	URL or Reference
Data Management Policy & Procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• GDPR (EUR-Lex - 32016R0679 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu))• Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 (h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf (europa.eu))• HL7 (Health Level Seven International - Homepage HL7 International)• OMOP-OHDSI (https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/the-common-data-model/).• TRIPOD guidelines (https://www.tripod-statement.org/).
Data Security Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Directive 95/46/EC: Protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.• GDPR (EUR-Lex - 32016R0679 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu))
Data Sharing Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• GDPR (EUR-Lex - 32016R0679 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu))• Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 (h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf (europa.eu))• OMOP-OHDSI (https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/the-common-data-model/).• TRIPOD guidelines (https://www.tripod-statement.org/).• Creative Commons 4.0 (Creative Commons — Attribution 4.0 International — CC BY 4.0)
Institutional Information Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• GDPR (EUR-Lex - 32016R0679 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu))• Art. 7, 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights• Art. 8 European Convention on Human Rights• Case Law by the European Court of Human Rights
Other	

8. Author of this Data Management Plan

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Annex I PerCard work plan

Figure 1: PerCard work plan

